

HARMONIC MODEL AND PHASE DISTORTION VOCODER (HMPD) AS A MUSICAL INSTRUMENT

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ABSTRACT

Recent advancements in automatic speech and singing synthesis have led to improved naturalness and realism in generated audio. However, these machine learning-based approaches often lack direct control over physical parameters between input and output. This paper explores the Harmonic Model and Phase Distortion (HMPD) vocoder as a tool for musical expression. Unlike many existing synthesis approaches, HMPD enables detailed parameter manipulation, facilitating smooth transitions between voice and other sound textures. This work examines HMPD's application in musical composition, demonstrating its effectiveness in resynthesizing both vocal and instrumental sounds.

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

The intersection of voice synthesis and musical creativity has been explored for decades. Stockhausen, for example, experimented with smooth transitions between voice and synthesized sounds in "Gesang der Jünglinge" [1]. Traditional vocoders, such as *Speech Transformation and Representation using Adaptive Interpolation of weiGHTEd spectrum* (STRAIGHT) [2] and *Collaborative Voice Analysis Repository* (COVAREP) [3], have enabled advancements in speech synthesis, yet they primarily focus on speech reconstruction rather than musical exploration.

Developments in generative audio models, such as WaveNet [4], have significantly improved speech and singing synthesis. WaveNet employs deep neural networks to model raw audio waveforms, achieving unprecedented levels of realism. Similarly, GAN-based approaches, such as WGANSing [5], have enabled multi-voice singing synthesis, demonstrating the power of machine learning in musical applications. However, these approaches generally lack fine-grained control over individual harmonics, making them less suitable for detailed sound design.

Very recently, some highly advanced algorithms for speech synthesis have emerged, such as Vall-E [6], AudioLM [7], and ElevenLabs [8]. While these methods achieve impressive results in terms of realism and fluency, they are not well-suited for artistic applications due to the lack of direct control over the generated audio. In contrast, this paper focuses on a model-based approach, which al-

lows for fine-tuned manipulations of sound parameters to foster artistic expression.

HMPD [9] offers a unique approach by capturing fundamental frequency, spectral envelope, phase deviation, and phase distortion, enabling precise manipulation. In contrast to FluCoMa's Harmonic Model [10], which is available also in SuperCollider but does not provide direct access to individual partials, HMPD allows for detailed harmonic modifications. Moreover, HMPD is included in the COVAREP speech processing framework and is freely available for download on GitHub: <https://github.com/covarep/covarep>. This paper explores its potential as a musical instrument by modifying harmonic components, allowing new forms of artistic expression.

FluCoMa's Harmonic Model follows a parametric sinusoidal model, decomposing sounds into harmonic and residual components using classical signal processing techniques such as STFT and peak tracking. Unlike deep learning-based vocoders, this approach is deterministic and does not involve machine learning. While FluCoMa supports machine learning-based classification and clustering, its harmonic model remains a traditional synthesis method. In contrast, HMPD extends beyond sinusoidal modeling by incorporating phase distortion, making it more suitable for expressive sound transformations and musical applications.

2. SIGNAL MODEL

2.1 HMPD Analysis

HMPD decomposes voice signals into overlapping frames, estimating sinusoidal parameters:

$$s_i(t) = \sum_{h=1}^{H_i} a_{i,h} \cdot e^{j(h\phi_0(t) + \phi_{i,h})} \quad (1)$$

where:

- $s_i(t)$ is the reconstructed signal for frame i at time t .
- $H_i = 0.5f_s/f_0(t_i)$ is the number of harmonics in each frame, where f_s is the sampling frequency and $f_0(t_i)$ is the fundamental frequency at time t_i .
- $a_{i,h}$ represents the amplitude of the h -th harmonic in frame i .
- $\phi_0(t)$ is the fundamental phase, obtained by integrating the fundamental frequency over time.

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- $\phi_{i,h}$ is the additional phase component for the h -th harmonic in frame i .

The fundamental frequency curve $f_0(t)$ is estimated using the algorithm from [11].

To ensure accurate spectral representation, HMPD employs *spectral envelope estimation* methods. The amplitude spectral envelope can be estimated using the True Envelope (TE) method [12] or the Discrete All-Pole (DAP) model [13]. These models ensure a robust representation of formant structures and help avoid over-smoothing artifacts. The estimated envelope provides the amplitude characteristics used in synthesis.

Phase Processing: Unlike traditional vocoders that discard phase information, HMPD models phase using *Relative Phase Shift (RPS)* and *Phase Distortion (PD)* [14]. The *RPS* removes the linear phase term, allowing phase modeling independent of fundamental frequency variations. The *PD* quantifies desynchronization between harmonics, capturing maximum-phase components and noisiness. Short-term statistics of PD—mean and standard deviation—are computed over several pitch periods, providing a continuous representation of voice quality and aperiodicity. The importance of phase in speech enhancement is explained in [15].

2.2 HMPD Synthesis

The synthesis function reconstructs the sound signal as follows:

$$\hat{s}(t) = 2R \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^K a_k(t) \cdot e^{jk\phi_0(t)} \right\} \quad (2)$$

where $a_k(t)$ is obtained through linear interpolation. Unlike standard synthesis methods, HMPD allows harmonic-specific control, enabling fine-tuned modifications.

The *harmonic amplitudes* $a_k(t)$ are synthesized from the spectral envelope using linear or spline interpolation, ensuring smooth temporal evolution. The *instantaneous phase* $\phi_k(t)$ is reconstructed using the sum of the estimated *mean phase distortion* and an artificial noise component based on the *standard deviation of PD*. This approach enables realistic noise modeling and eliminates the need for explicit voiced/unvoiced decisions, making HMPD superior in handling transitions between speech and non-speech sounds.

Additionally, an *adaptive frequency warping* mechanism refines the synthesized harmonic structure to match natural frequency modulations, improving the perceived realism in expressive singing synthesis.

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Analysis of a Singing Voice

The spectrogram of a sung vowel u in Figure 1 demonstrates the fundamental frequency and harmonic structures. Figure 2 illustrates the extracted amplitude envelope, revealing subtle variations crucial for natural resynthesis.

Through experiments, it was found that fixing the fundamental frequency at a constant value results in an unnatural voice. Similarly, keeping the spectral envelope

Figure 1. Spectrogram of a sung vowel u .

Figure 2. Fundamental frequency (left) and amplitude envelope (right) of a sung vowel u (outputs of HMPD analysis).

fixed produces an unnatural effect. A more natural voice is achieved by mapping very slight variations in the fundamental frequency to corresponding slight variations in the spectral envelope. However, this naturalness is only preserved when the fundamental frequency itself varies in a natural way. In this context, "natural" refers to incorporating low-frequency variations akin to those produced by SuperCollider's `LFNoise1`.

This insight highlights the importance of preserving microvariations in both frequency and spectral envelope dynamics. By ensuring these fluctuations are retained, the resynthesized voice maintains its expressive and organic qualities, preventing static or overly artificial timbres.

3.2 Sound Transformations

Experiments demonstrate controlled transformations, including vibrato manipulation (Figure 3), spectral morphing (Figure 4), and harmonic amplitude modification (Figure 5). These results highlight HMPD's potential for expressive sound design beyond speech synthesis.

The transformations discussed in this paper can be listened to on <https://annamaly.mur.at/smc.htm>, a website specifically designed for this research. Additionally, the creative artistic utilization of the HMPD algorithm can be explored on <https://annamaly.mur.at/>. In particular, the piece *Lux Aeterna Unlimited* is notable for its use of unnatural partial amplitude manip-

Figure 3. Decreasing vibrato: Fundamental frequency input for HMPD synthesis (left) and time-frequency spectrogram output of HMPD synthesis (right).

Figure 4. Spectrogram of a cello transforming into synthesizer sounds of a Doepfer analog synthesiser.

Figure 5. Spectrogram of natural voice transforming into sound with unnatural partial amplitudes.

ulation, as depicted in Figure 5.

Another significant work is *Reality Study*, where the entire piece is constructed around a fixed fundamental frequency. It begins with an opera voice that gradually transitions into the author’s own singing voice—not all partials at once, but individually moving through space. The voice then alters single partials into unnatural amplitude distributions before gradually shifting into cello-like timbres. The cello partials are initially time-shifted, slowly aligning over time until the instrument becomes recognizable. The transition continues as individual cello harmonics are replaced with those of a flute, raising the question: at what point does the sound become a flute, and at what point does it cease to be a cello?

3.3 Workflow with HMPD

The current artistic workflow with HMPD starts with downloading the COVAREP repository from GitHub and executing the `startup.m` script in MATLAB. The supplied tutorial file `HOWTO_hmpd.m` is highly recommended for initial orientation. It guides the user through the essential steps of analysis and resynthesis. The typical starting point is the analysis and subsequent resynthesis of a short segment (e.g. a few seconds) of a desired audio file. The quality of the resynthesis serves as a diagnostic for parameter tuning. If the output does not sound natural, the most common causes are incorrectly configured fundamental frequency limits (set in the HMPD options) or input recordings of insufficient quality. In particular, reverberation or background noise can significantly affect performance as the algorithm expects a clean and dry monophonic input. Synthesis is performed using the function `hmpd_synthesis`, which returns the reconstructed waveform. To gain access to individual partials, the synthesis function must be modified slightly: Within the loop for harmonic synthesis (for $h = 1:Hmax$), each harmonic is generated separately. At the end of this loop, the harmonic component is added to the output signal. It is at this point that you can intercept and extract each harmonic individually, either by writing them directly to disk or by adding an additional output to the function. In addition to the already accessible parameters — such as the fundamental frequency at certain points in time and the spectral envelope (which defines the amplitudes of the harmonics) — we now also have access to the individual partials of the signal as separate components. These parameters offer a high degree of control for the sound design. For example, by adjusting the timeline using the pitch markers, you can stretch time, as explored in the piece *Fragile Idylle*. When two different sound sources are analyzed, their corresponding parameters can be interpolated to create seamless transitions. Changing the frequencies directly often led to synthetic-sounding results that resembled simple waveform generators (e.g. SuperCollider’s *SinOsc.ar* modulated by *LFNoise1.kr*). Instead, the manipulation of partial amplitudes led to more satisfactory results, as shown in *Lux Aeterna Unlimited*. In *Reality Study* the following technique was used: Individual partials of different sounds (including opera voice, untrained voice, cello and

flute) were selectively shifted in time, replaced or superimposed. This allowed a controlled and gradual transformation from one timbre to another.

4. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This article presents HMPD as a powerful tool for musical expression. By providing direct access to the parameters of voice synthesis, HMPD enables seamless sound transformation. However, while the HMPD algorithm has considerable artistic potential, its practical application as a musical instrument remains a challenge.

A major obstacle is the dependence on MATLAB, which is neither a common programming language for composers nor an accessible platform due to its high license costs. A translation into Python could make HMPD more accessible to musicians and researchers. While a full Python version of HMPD does not yet exist, related tools such as `pyworld`, `librosa` and `torchaudio` could potentially be used to reconstruct parts of the functionality.

Another limitation is the lack of real-time functions, which restricts its use in live performances and interactive compositions. This is primarily because HMPD relies on pitch-synchronous analysis and contextual phase modeling, both of which introduce latency and require access to the audio signal in an entire window. To achieve real-time performance, buffer sizes would need to be minimized, lookahead dependencies reduced, and possibly the phase model simplified or approximated. While these efforts are technically challenging, they would allow for a more interactive use of the music.

Despite these challenges, this article shows the enormous potential of model-based algorithms for musical applications. The artistic use of algorithms for speech signal processing remains underexplored. Before moving entirely to AI-based approaches, it would be worthwhile to revisit and further develop the model-based synthesis techniques of the past decades and refine them for contemporary artistic use. Future work includes the development of real-time implementations and interactive tools for composition and performance.

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